

NMR Spectroscopy of Oriented Organoselenium Compounds

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The use of nmr spectroscopy of oriented molecules in the determination of molecular structure and conformation of organoselenium compounds is presented. Determination of various spectral parameters including their anisotropic contributions is discussed. An up-to-date available information on the selenium compounds is included.

EXTENSIVE use of nmr spectroscopy of molecules oriented in liquid crystals has been made towards the determination of structure and conformation of small organic molecules¹⁻⁴. To a much lesser extent, biologically important systems⁵ and inorganic compounds⁷ have been investigated using this method, probably due to structural complexities and relatively poor solubilities. On the other hand, the technique promises to provide such structural, conformational and functional information which is otherwise difficult to obtain. Various applications including those in inorganic chemistry have been reviewed from time to time¹⁻⁷. The present report summarises some applications to organo-selenium compounds with emphasis on the work done by the Bangalore group.

Experimental

NMR spectra of oriented molecules can be recorded on normal high resolution spectrometers. Suitable solutions¹⁻⁶ are prepared in liquid crystals and the spectra recorded with or without sample spinning depending upon whether the experiments

are performed under the conditions that the liquid crystal director is along or orthogonal to the direction of spinning. A typical spectrum of dimethylselenide is shown in Fig. 1. Line-widths of around 1-5 Hz are usually obtained in the spectra of oriented molecules.

For the selenium compounds, ⁷⁷Se has a natural abundance of 7.58% and spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and ⁷⁷Se-¹H couplings can either be determined from studies of the selenium resonance or from the ⁷⁷Se-¹H satellites in the proton spectra. The latter technique is more common due to larger sensitivity of protons compared to selenium and also because the normally available spectrometers with facilities to study protons can be used. Furthermore, studies of the satellite spectra have the advantage that the information on the H-H and Se-H couplings can be obtained from the same experiment and the errors arising from the change of experimental conditions are avoided. However, for the ⁷⁷Se-⁷⁷Se couplings and the ⁷⁷Se-chemical shift anisotropy studies, ⁷⁷Se-nmr may be necessary.

Fig. 1. NMR spectrum of oriented dimethylselenide. The spectrum is symmetrical about the dashed line and only half the spectrum to the right of the line shown. Liquid crystal solvent used: A mixture of N-(*p*-ethoxybenzylidene)-*p*-*n*-butylaniline and butyl-*p*-(*p*-ethoxyphenoxycarbonyl)-phenylcarbonate. Solute concentration: 9 mole per cent; Temp.: 30°; Spectrometer frequency: 100 MHz.

Basic principles

Though the basic principles of the technique are well known and documented, their brief presentation in this article is meaningful for the sake of completeness. Due to inherent molecular ordering and flow of the medium, the molecules dissolved in liquid crystal solvents show orientational effects and provide such information in the spectra which is otherwise not obtainable from the spectra in normal isotropic media. Such spectra for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ nuclei (i and j) contain information not only on the average values of the chemical shift ($\nu_i - \nu_j$) and indirect values of the spin-spin (J_{ij}) and direct dipole-dipole (D_{ij}) coupling tensors but anisotropic contributions of these second rank tensors can also be derived from the spectra. Of these, the most important parameters from the structural and the conformational points of view are the direct dipolar couplings and chemical shift anisotropy. Their determination and use will, therefore, be discussed in detail with emphasis to organoselenium compounds.

Having obtained the spectra, they are analysed using the standard procedures reported in the literature¹⁻⁵. The analysis procedures are usually similar to those for the analysis of the spectra in the isotropic media except that the Hamiltonian contains additional terms due to various anisotropic contributions. The computer programs such as LAOCOONOR⁶ or LEQUOR⁷ are normally used.

The direct dipole-dipole coupling derived from the spectra of oriented molecules is related to the internuclear distance (r_{ij}) as in equation (1).

$$D_{ij} = \frac{\gamma_i \gamma_j}{4\pi^2} \cdot \frac{S_{ij}}{r_{ij}^3} \quad \dots (1)$$

where γ is the magnetogyric ratio and S_{ij} is the degree of order of the axis ij.

The chemical shift anisotropy ($\Delta\sigma_i$) for a nucleus in a 3-fold or higher symmetry axis is given by equation (2):

$$\Delta\sigma_i = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{\sigma_{ia}}{S_{aa}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where σ_{ia} is the chemical shift in the anisotropic medium with respect to that in the isotropic phase and S_{aa} is the order parameter of the symmetry axis.

Relations between other anisotropic and order parameters are reported in the literature¹⁻⁵.

The direct dipolar couplings derived from the analysis of the spectra of oriented molecules are used to determine molecular geometries with the help of equation (1). However, since the order parameters also have to be determined from the spectra, the number of independent dipolar couplings must at least equal the sum of the required order and geometrical parameters so as to obtain the necessary geometrical information without making assumption.

Equation (1) shows that if the order parameter and r_{ij}^3 are changed by a constant factor, D_{ij} 's

and hence the spectra of oriented molecules remain unchanged. Since the order parameter has to be determined from the same experiment, the method provides relative internuclear distances rather than their absolute values.

A typical illustration of the determination of the structure of selenophene^{10,11} (Structure 1) is given below before describing results on some other selenium compounds.

The analysis of the ^1H -nmr spectrum of selenophene with ^{77}Se -H satellites and without ^{13}C -H satellites provides four different interproton dipolar couplings, namely, D_{12} , D_{13} , D_{14} and D_{23} and two ^{77}Se -H couplings, namely, D_{15} and D_{25} . On the other hand only 3 independent ratios of the internuclear distances are necessary to describe the relative interproton and proton-selenium distances. Even after the determination of the molecular order, the system provides one additional coupling than that necessary for the determination of molecular geometry. Hence, in such a case the relative internuclear distances, i.e., r_{12}/r_{23} , r_{14}/r_{23} and r_{15}/r_{25} are determined by a least-square-fit computer programme which provides the geometrical and the order parameters such that the sum of the squares of the deviations between the observed and the calculated dipolar couplings is minimum. A computer programme referred to as SHAPE¹² is the one which is most commonly used for such a purpose. The values determined are shown in Table 1, including those derived from microwave spectroscopic studies. It may be mentioned that the proton nmr spectrum of oriented selenophene including ^{77}Se -H and ^{13}C -H satellites has in fact been studied and the carbon positions have also been determined. They are not included in the table for the sake of simplicity.

TABLE 1—RATIOS OF THE INTERNUCLEAR DISTANCES IN SELENOPHENE DETERMINED FROM NMR SPECTROSCOPY

Parameter	Value	
	NMR	Microwave
r_{12}/r_{23}	1.002 ± 0.006	0.997
r_{14}/r_{23}	1.837 ± 0.004	1.785
r_{15}/r_{25}	1.849 ± 0.004	1.802

It may be mentioned that nmr spectroscopy of oriented molecules provides values in the liquid phase whereas other techniques such as X-ray, electron and neutron diffractions and microwave spectroscopy values are in the solid or the gaseous phases.

Applications

Selenium is an ideal nucleus from the point of view of nmr spectroscopy. The natural abundance of spin 1/2 isotope (^{77}Se) is reasonably large (7.58%) and the compounds provide relatively sharp lines. The proton nmr spectra of 1,3-dithiole-2-selone, 1,3-thiaselenole-2-thione and 1,3-diselenole-2-selone oriented in the nematic phases of N-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)-*p*-*n*-butylaniline (MBBA) or N-(*p*-ethoxybenzylidene)-*p*-*n*-butylaniline (EBBA) show lines with widths less than 1.5 Hz on a WH-270 spectrometer and hence the observation of ^{77}Se -H and ^{13}C -H satellites in these systems present no special difficulties¹⁸.

Several selenium compounds such as dimethylselenide^{14, 16}, difluorophosphine selenide¹⁹, selenophene^{10, 11}, 2,1 3-benzoselenadiazole¹⁷, benzo(b)selenophene¹⁸, 1,2,5-selenadiazole¹⁹, phenyl selenyl chloride and bromide²⁰, 3-phenyl-1,2,5-selenadiazole²¹, tetraselenafulvalene²², selenophene-2-carbaldehyde²³, 2,2'-biselenophene²⁴, trimethylphosphine selenide²⁵⁻²⁷ and triphenyl selenophosphine²⁸ have been investigated in order to derive structural and conformational informations and chemical shift anisotropies. In addition, 2-dimensional proton nmr spectrum of oriented 1-thia-3-selenole-2-thione has also been studied without ^{77}Se -H and ^{13}C -H satellites for the unique determination of ($J_{\text{HH}} + 2D_{\text{HH}}$)—an information which cannot be obtained from the single resonance 1-dimensional spectrum^{29, 30}.

From the analysis of the proton nmr spectrum of dimethyl selenide with ^{77}Se -H satellites, the indirect spin-spin coupling between the protons of the two methyl groups has been determined as 0.1 Hz. A study of the spectrum including ^{77}Se -H as well as ^{13}C -H satellites has also been undertaken and the molecular structure derived. Assuming the internuclear (C-Se) distance ($r_{\text{C-Se}}$) as 1.943 Å, a value of $r_{\text{C-H}}$ as 1.073 Å has been obtained. The bond angles C-Se-C, H-C-Se and H-C-H have been derived as 95.7°, 106.22° and 110.14°, respectively. The C_2 -symmetry axes of the methyl groups are displaced from the C-Se axes by 2.57° in such a way that the C-Se-C angle is reduced.

In difluorophosphine selenide, the SePF, FPF and SePH bond angles have been obtained as 116.8°, 98.1° and 118.6°, respectively.

The geometry-information in selenophene has been derived and the results are reported in the previous section. An interesting application has emerged from the studies on several heteroaromatic 5-membered ring systems (Structure 2). r_{14}/r_{23} has

X=O, N(H), C(H), S, P, Se, Te
Structure 2

been found to vary inversely with the van der Waals or covalent radii³¹. Values of these quantities have been determined for X=O, S, CH, NH, P, Se and Te.

The structure of 2,1,3-benzoselenadiazole has been derived from the proton nmr spectrum. Values of the indirect proton-proton couplings and the relative interproton distances indicate considerable bond fixation in the 6-membered ring of benzoselenadiazole. In 1,2,5-selenadiazole, for which the ^1H -nmr spectra including ^{13}C and ^{77}Se -satellites have been obtained, the interproton distance has been derived by assuming the ring geometry in addition to a scaling distance. The structure of the 6 and the 5 membered rings in benzo(b)-selenophene has been derived from its nmr spectrum in a lyotropic solvent.

Recently, very interesting new applications of nmr spectroscopy of oriented molecules have been discovered³². The studies involve recording the spectra in a mixture of 2 liquid crystals of opposite diamagnetic anisotropies. At a critical relative concentration of the two liquid crystals, it is possible to obtain spectra with two different types of molecular orientations if the temperature is suitably adjusted. The two orientations provide dipolar couplings in the exact ratio 1:2. The results are theoretically well understood³³. These experiments provide spectral information which is otherwise not possible to derive from the spectra of oriented molecules. For example, separate determination of the indirect and the direct dipolar couplings between heteronuclei is possible only from such experiments. The method has been used to determine ^{77}Se -H indirect couplings in phenylselenyl chloride and bromide. The structural information in these systems has also been determined.

The preferred conformation of 3-phenyl-1,2,5-selenadiazole has been found to be twisted around the bond between the two rings and the angle of twist is $\approx 20^\circ$. A comparison of the results with those in 3-phenyl-1,2,5-oxa and thiadiazoles in different solvents shows that the conformation is little influenced by the nature of the heteroatom at position 2 or the solvent. The molecule tetraselenafulvalene is shown to be either puckered in a boat form or possessing a broad potential function for the puckering motion. The dihedral angle between the $\text{SeHC}=\text{CHSe}$ and $\text{Se}_2\text{C}=\text{CSe}_2$ planes is $15.5 \pm 0.6^\circ$.

In selenophen-2-carbaldehyde, the conformational information is derived by assuming that the positions of the 3-ring protons are the same as those in selenophene and considering either the existence of a single planar conformer or the *cis-trans* equilibrium. The existence of the Se-O *cis-trans* is confirmed though some evidence was also found for the presence of a small amount of Se-O *trans* conformer. 2,2'-Biselenophene has been shown to be present as an equilibrium between two twisted conformers, the transoid one being more abundant and the angle of twist being $25 \pm 5^\circ$.

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The chemical shift and the indirect spin-spin coupling anisotropies have also been determined in some of the selenium compounds. The phosphorus-selenium indirect coupling constant in $\text{PSe}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ has been measured as -704 Hz. A comparison of the X-ray diffraction and nmr results in $\text{PSe}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ shows that the phosphorus-selenium indirect coupling is highly anisotropic. The ^{13}C and ^{31}P -chemical shift anisotropies in $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{PSe}$ are 18 ± 10 and 99 ± 15 ppm, respectively. The C-P-C bond angle is $105.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$. The ^{31}P -chemical shift anisotropy in triphenylphosphine selenide is determined as 103 ppm.

Conclusion

The survey provides an up-to-date information available from the spectra of oriented selenium compounds. The technique is potentially useful in the structural and conformational problems in selenium chemistry.

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